
OCTOMATH: CONTEXTUAL BANDIT ROUTING FOR MODULAR OLYMPIAD-STYLE MATH SOLVING

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ABSTRACT

Large Language Models (LLMs) have recently achieved great performance on complex mathematical problems with long chains of thought (COT) reasoning. However, this comes at a high cost, as it can allocate excessive computation, especially on trivial arithmetic tasks, even if the answers are correct. Therefore, we aimed at finding a way to make a reduction in reasoning overhead and computational waste while maintaining the use of LLM reasoning. In this paper, we propose our OctoMath system as a suggested solution for this problem and to rely on faster and more accurate approaches rather than a monolithic LLM. OctoMath is a hybrid neuro-symbolic routing system that can solve math problems by making a multi-armed contextual bandit (LinUCB) direct them to their correct solving strategies, either deterministic or neural. Moreover, the project is done for the submission of the AI Mathematical Olympiad - Progress Prize 3 (AIMO3) competition on Kaggle, where we strictly followed their constraints, such as: Kaggle internet off and no use of external APIs by making a new dataset of offline Ollama Packages. Results for our case study experiment indicate a 19,825x speedup when using our OctoMath system compared to the standard LLM DeepSeek-R1-Distill-Qwen-7B on the same Kaggle constrained CPU environment. In general, this system presents the hybrid neural-symbolic paradigm advocated by one of the papers, and all code, datasets, and runtime are publicly available. Moreover, this work is a research proof of concept that focuses on routing, offline deployment, and verification-assisted inference rather than state-of-the-art benchmark performance.

Keywords Contextual Multi-armed LinUCB bandit · Reinforcement Learning · AIMO3 Competition · Offline Inference · Mathematics.

1 Introduction

1.1 Motivation: The Overthinking Problem

Nowadays, LLMs are an important part of our daily lives, solving a lot of problems. They are known for their ability to reason through complex problems using their deep COTs, as mentioned in the Huang et al. [2025] paper. However, this strength can be a point of weakness, where LLMs can take lengthy COT steps in trivial arithmetic problems, despite their simplicity, causing excessive tokens Li et al. [2025]. This problem can be defined as “overthinking”, where LLM can produce unnecessary reasoning steps on simple tasks. Moreover, Frieder et al. [2025a] have pointed out in their paper the necessity of solving the dependency on a single monolithic problem as they are inefficient, and the need for a hybrid neuro-symbolic system that can select a specialized tool for their suitable tasks. Accordingly, our system targets this problem and tries to solve trivial math problems faster and better.

*GitHub: <https://github.com/AhmedHazemHassan/OctoMath-Contextual-Bandit-Routing-for-Modular-Olympiad-Style-Math-Solving-with-Fully-Offline-Ollama.git>

Figure 1: OctoMath System Architecture

1.2 AIMO3 Competition

The AIMO3 competition, organized by Frieder et al. [2025b], was a suitable opportunity for reducing the overthinking dilemma, as it provided strict constraints for the competition. For instance, it required a complete offline inference environment on Kaggle with neither external APIs nor the Kaggle internet. Moreover, the suggested solution method must be efficient and fast enough to meet their runtime conditions. Therefore, we designed the OctoMath system to be as fast as possible, verifiable, and efficient. Furthermore, to satisfy the offline constraint, we packaged a complete Ollama runtime (MIT-licensed) Ollama Contributors [2023] with CUDA/CPU runners and predownloaded model artifacts, enabling full offline LLM inference. The OctoMath is developed to be fast, verifiable, and efficient within these operating constraints.

2 Methodology

2.1 System Architecture

The OctoMath pipeline establishes an error-aware sequential workflow, as shown in Figure 1, with fallback strategies.

Our system receives its input, the math problem question, in LaTeX format, and then it is passed to two methods. Firstly, the problem is scanned by our hard-coded feature extractor into a 9-dimensional regex binary vector; meanwhile, the all-MiniLM-L6-v2 model, released by Sentence-Transformers Team [2024], is stored offline in a new Kaggle dataset created by the author. It reads and infers the semantics behind the problem, outputting a 384-dimensional sentence-

transformer vector. Accordingly, these two vectors are concatenated into a single 393-dimensional vector. Secondly, our multi-armed contextual LinUCB bandit ranks the six actions according to UCB, previous learning extracted from the bandit_state.json file, and outputs the best action and a list of ranked actions for strategy fallback. This enhances its selection policy and allows learning from experience. Finally, the output is verified using sympy-backed sanity checks, where it makes algebraic verification when the problem structure permits and equation substitution when applicable, and lastly, numeric validation SymPy Development Team [2019]. The reward is given to Bandit to improve its learning.

2.2 RL Problem Formulation: Contextual Multi-Armed Bandit

In this section, the RL problem is presented in more detail. The following covers the problem formalization at each time t :

2.2.1 Context Space (\mathcal{X})

The system at first receives its math problem as LaTeX input (q_t) and is processed into one larger dimensional vector as follows:

$$x_t = [\Omega_{regex}(q_t) \parallel \phi_{embed}(q_t)]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{393}$$

Where:

- q_t is the math problem itself.
- x_t is the context space of the RL environment, and the combination of both the regex-based feature extractor and the sentence-transformer’s model outputs.
- $\Omega_{regex}(q_t) \in \{0, 1\}^9$ is the 9-dim feature binary vector detecting from 9 different mathematical categories: Modular Arithmetic, Recurrence Relations, Combinatorics, etc.
- $\phi_{embed}(q_t) \in \mathbb{R}^{384}$ corresponds to the output of the sentence-transformer all-MiniLM-L6-v2 model Sentence-Transformers Team [2024] that contains the embeddings of the semantics of the math problem.

2.2.2 Action Space (\mathcal{A})

Action Space is the set of all available actions performed by the system, where OctoMath introduces six different specialized solver strategies, “arms” as shown in Table 1:

$$A \in \{a_0, a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5\}$$

Table 1: OctoMath Action Space: Description of specialized solver arms.

Action ID	Corresponding Solver Arm
a_0	llm_direct
a_1	llm_sympy
a_2	dp_module
a_3	mod_arith
a_4	geometry_module
a_5	combinatorics

llm_direct (a_0) is the most general arm, where LLM is called to solve the problem directly, but consumes a lot of time and memory. Furthermore, the llm_sympy (a_1) strategy is solved by LLM that generates Python/SymPy code executed in a sandbox; however, it can be slower, especially if there is an error in the generated code that will be fed back to the LLM for correction. These are the neural “system 1” actions in our architecture. The remaining four arms are deterministic that solves different math categories.

2.2.3 Reward Function Definition (\mathcal{R})

OctoMath has 3 types of discrete verification-shaped rewards as follows:

$$r(a_t) = \begin{cases} 1.0 & ; \text{if verified deterministic solution} \\ 0.5 & ; \text{if (un)verified LLM-direct solution} \\ 0 & ; \text{if Invalid output or failed verification or error} \end{cases}$$

The key design choice is that `llm_direct` outputs receive partial credit of 0.5 as a fallback incentive, while verified deterministic outputs receive a full credit of one (1.0), and the unverified or failed deterministic outputs receive zero (0.0). Accordingly, this makes the bandit biased toward preferring deterministic solvers, which are both fast and verifiable, over the general LLM reasoning, which is slower and unverifiable.

2.3 Fully Offline Deployment (Ollama Packaging)

To fulfill AIMO3 competition’s constraints Frieder et al. [2025b], like the Kaggle internet off and no external APIs, and a strict run time budget. Furthermore, we noticed that Ollama has MIT open source on GitHub Ollama Contributors [2023], therefore, this paved the way for handcrafting a new dataset containing Ollama’s packaging from runners and model’s download utils. However, to reach this clean dataset, we faced many challenges, and they all occurred in an offline Kaggle environment. For example, we tried to run the dataset only with the model’s blobs and manifests downloaded and fetched previously while being online, but it failed as it didn’t contain Ollama’s binary file. Accordingly, we switched online again and downloaded the file using `pip install ollama` and copied the binary file to the offline dataset. Fortunately, this experiment has succeeded, and the model ran normally, but we discovered it runs on CPU only and doesn’t work on GPU. Consequently, we learnt that we need the runners folder to enable both CPU and GPU. Finally, it worked properly after fetching our last edits to the dataset while satisfying all the competition’s restrictions. Additionally, we maintained all copyrights of all original authors from Deepseek-R1 Guo et al. [2025], Qwen Yang et al. [2024], and Ollama.

3 Experimental Results

3.1 Case Study on OctoMath Performance

We have experimented with Kaggle using the same competition environment as Kaggle internet off, and no APIs utilizing CPU only. Moreover, this experiment is intended as an illustrative routing-efficiency case study on a modular arithmetic task rather than a comprehensive benchmark across mathematical reasoning workloads. Therefore, the experiment’s main objective is to prove our hypothesis that LLM can overthink in a trivial math task and to show our performance of the OctoMath system compared to that of DeepSeek-R1-Distill-Qwen-7B LLM. Furthermore, We aimed to solve the following direct math problem using the same prompt for both methods to maintain a fair comparison, where the prompt is “Find $2^{100} \bmod 1000$. Provide the final answer as an integer”, and we measured the wall-clock time for both. The results indicate that LLM took approximately 1387.78 seconds (23 minutes) to produce its result. Although the output is correct mathematically, the extended reasoning trace suggests that the model has spent significant tokens on intermediate calculations and verification steps, which is unnecessary for the modular arithmetic task. Contrary to our OctoMath system’s results, which have solved it in about 0.07 seconds with verified correctness, as shown in Table 2. This is done because of our smart ranking system and the contextual LinUCB bandit that can detect the right problem class and route the system to the correct arm “`mod_arith`” that has solved it correctly, efficiently, and quickly.

Table 2: OctoMath experiment results.

Method	Runtime (seconds)	Correctness	Verified
Deepseek-R1-Distill-Qwen-7B	1,387.78	Correct	No
OctoMath	0.07	Correct	Yes
Speedup	19,825	-	-

Accordingly, this directly shows a complete end-to-end experiment and proves that our system can have a valuable chance as it aligns well with what was stated in the paper Frieder et al. [2025a] about the necessity of inclusion of symbolic factors in the math copilot system.

3.2 Reproducibility and AIMO3 Competition

Our computational artifacts are publicly released via Kaggle datasets, notebooks, write-up, and finally GitHub [Hassan, 2026a,b,c,d,e,f,g].

4 Conclusion

In conclusion, we present OctoMath, a neuro-symbolic routing system that uses a contextual multi-armed LinUCB bandit to rank and select its actions smartly. This Method aligns well with Frieder et al. (2025), where we introduce a smart routing system that can choose between neural and symbolic approaches, not just follow a sequence-to-sequence model. Furthermore, our empirical evaluation demonstrates a 19,825x speedup compared to direct Deepseek-R1-Distill-Qwen-7B inference on a modular arithmetic math problem. However, we only tried one arithmetic problem in this experiment, which validates our hypothesis of overthinking. Moreover, this work stands for proof of concept only, where we tested on a modular arithmetic math problem in just one math class. Further research should evaluate OctoMath on more diverse problem types using either our synthetic dataset, Test_95_Problems, generated by ChatGPT, or the standard benchmarks, such as AIME 2024 or Math500. Overall, our system contributes to the Mathematical AI field by illustrating that hybrid routing can be better than a sequential monolithic LLM model alone, while providing fully reproducible public datasets and code for solving a serious issue like overthinking.

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